

Studies on Complexes of Vanadium(IV), Zirconium(IV), Vanadium(V), Niobium(V), Tantalum(V), Molybdenum(VI) and Tungsten(VI) with 2-Mercapto-3-substituted-quinazolin-4-one

R. N. PANDEY*, R. N. SHARMA, L. M. ROY CHOUDHARY and (Mrs.) PRAMILA SHARMA

P. G. Centre of Chemistry, College of Commerce (M.U.), Patna-800 020

Manuscript received 29 January 1992, revised 6 July 1992, accepted 6 August 1992

2-Mercapto-3-phenyl-quinazolin-4-one (TQPH) and 2-mercaptoquinazolin-4-one (TQH) interact through the thione tautomeric form with VO_2^+ , VO^{II} , Zr^{IV} , Nb^V and Ta^V species but interact with thiol form in case of MoO_4^{II} and WO_4^{II} resulting deprotonation of thiol hydrogen atom. Infrared spectra suggest the presence of *cis*- MoO_3 , *cis*- WO_3 and *trans*- VO_3 structures. The nature of shifts and change in intensity of all the four thioamide bands of the ligand are diagnosis of M-L bonding. An octahedral structure for all the complexes have been tentatively assigned.

2-Mercapto-3-substituted-quinazolin-4-one is known for their varied spectrum of antimalarial activities¹. Some substituted quinazolines have been reported to possess various biological activities². Complexing behaviour of these physiologically active compounds with many class 'a' and 'b' types metals have been studied by various workers³. However, no attention has been paid to study structural aspects and nature of bonding with higher oxidation state metal ions. Thus, the present paper describes the complexes of V^{IV} , Zr^{IV} , V^V , Nb^V , Ta^V , Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} using different derivatives of 2-mercapto-3-substituted-quinazolin-4-one (1).

TQH (R=H) and TQPH (R=C₆H₅)

Results and Discussion

Both of the 2-mercapto-3-substituted-quinazolin-4-one ligands form fairly stable complex. The ligands, interact VO_2^+ , VO^{II} , ZrO^{II} , Zr^{IV} , Nb^V and Ta^V in thione form. However, MoO_4^{II} and WO_4^{II} interact with thiol tautomeric with deprotonated thiol. Two different complexes of VO_2^+ were obtained when molar ratio of VO_2^+ to TQH or TQPH were varied. Yet another complex $[\text{VO}_2(\text{TQH})_4]\text{Cl}$ was also isolated using excess of TQH. But we could not isolate such composition with TQPH most

probably due to steric bulk of the phenyl group at position-3. The hydrated complexes lose their associated water molecules on heating above 85° and become almost anhydrous around 110°. The complete loss of water molecules at low temperature indicates that they are uncoordinated. All the complexes are soluble in DMF; solubility decreases as the polarity of organic solvents decreases. The values of molar conductance of 10⁻³ M DMF solution of $[\text{Zr}(\text{TQH})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{NO}_3)_4$ (320 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) suggest 1 : 4 electrolyte⁴ but $[\text{Nb}(\text{TQH})_2\text{Cl}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Ta}(\text{TQH})_2\text{Cl}_4]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{VO}_2(\text{TQH})_4]\text{Cl}$ are 1 : 1 electrolyte having molar conductance values in the range 46–62 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹. The ionic nature of nitrate and chloride ions as revealed by conductance data is further supported by the chemical analysis of their Na₂CO₃ extract and infrared spectral data. However, all other complexes are non-electrolyte having very low molar conductance value (8–11 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹).

All the complexes are diamagnetic as expected for *d*⁰-complexes. However, magnetic moment of $[\text{VO}(\text{TQH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{SO}_4]$ was found to be 1.69 B.M. indicating a *d*¹-configuration. The low magnetic moment most probably is due to partial metal-metal bond arising from overlapping of *d*-orbitals on neighbouring vanadium atoms⁵. Moreover, the low magnetic moment suggests symmetry lower than octahedral⁶. Electronic spectrum of this complex displays very strong band at 355 nm and two medium broad bands at 480 and 570 nm. The first band may be due to charge transfer origin but the other two bands are due to ²B₂→²B₁ and ²B₂→²A₁ transitions following Ballhausen and Gray⁷ orbital transformation scheme for the C_{4v} species $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$. Thus, distorted octahedral geometry may be suggested for VO^{IV} -complex⁸. An absorption due to π→π* transition at 303 nm in the electronic spectrum of

TABLE 1—SELECTED IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{NH}	ν_{SH}	$\nu_{\text{M}^{\text{d}}=\text{O}^*}$	ν_{NO_2} ν_{SO_4}	Thioamide band				Nature of bonding
					I	II	III	IV	
TQH	3 400, 3 230	2 360	—	—	1 530	1 275, 1 230	990	800	—
[VO(TQH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ SO ₄]	3 400, 3 240	—	970	1 070, 1 000, 640	1 530	1 270, 1 220	950	760	Thione-S
[VO ₂ (TQH) ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl]	3 420, 3 245	—	820	—	1 525	1 265, 1 215	945	750	Thione-S
[VO ₂ (TQH)(H ₂ O) ₂ Cl]·3H ₂ O	3 400, 3 280	—	810	—	1 530	1 255, 1 220	940	750	Thione-S
[VO ₂ (TQH) ₂]Cl	3 400, 3 245	—	820	—	1 530	1 265, 1 225	950	760	Thione-S
[Zr(TQH) ₂ (H ₂ O)(SO ₄) ₂]	3 400, 3 220	—	—	1 060, 960, 640	1 550, 1 520	1 260, 1 220	940	750	Thione-S
[ZrO(TQH)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	3 410, 3 220	—	—	—	1 550, 1 515	1 260, 1 220	950	760	Thione-S
[Zr(TQH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	3 400, 3 230	—	—	1 340, 860	1 530	1 250, 1 220	940	750	Thione-S
[MoO ₂ (TQ) ₂]	—	—	980, 840	—	1 520, 1 505	1 260, 1 220	970	705	Thiol-S
[WO ₂ (TQ) ₂]	—	—	930, 840	—	1 520, 1 505	1 265, 1 230	970	702	Thiol-S
[Nb(TQH) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl·2H ₂ O	3 400, 3 240	—	—	—	1 530, 1 220	1 260	940	760	Thione-S
[Ta(TQH) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	3 400, 3 230	—	—	—	1 535	1 255, 1 215	950	760	Thione-S
TQPH	3 420, 3 215	2 340	—	—	1 525	1 270, 1 230	990	800	—
[VO ₂ (TQPH) ₂]Cl	3 420, 3 220	—	950, 810	—	1 530	1 270, 1 220	960	760	Thione-S
[VO ₂ (TQPH) ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl]	3 420, 3 215	—	955, 820	—	1 530	1 260, 1 220	950	760	Thione-S
[ZrO(TQPH)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	3 420, 3 230	—	—	—	1 530	1 250, 1 220	940	750	Thione-S
[WO ₂ (TQP) ₂]	—	—	985, 840	—	1 520, 1 505	1 260, 1 215	970	700	Thiol-S

*d=V, Mo and W.

2-mercapto-3-substituted-quinazoline-4-one⁹ shifts to 300, 296, 295 and 297 nm in the MoO₄^{II}, VO₄^I, WO₄^{II} and ZrO^{II} complexes respectively, indicating the presence of coordinated ligand. However, no complex absorbs between 800 and 400 nm, as might be expected for metal ions with (n-1) d⁰ nS⁰ electronic configuration¹⁰.

The selected ir spectral bands of the complexes have been shown in Table 1. The two distinct broad absorption bands around 3 400 and 3 230–3 215 cm⁻¹ of medium intensities are assigned to ν_{NH} in the spectrum of 2-mercapto-3-substituted-quinazoline-4-one. The band at 3 230–3 215 cm⁻¹ of medium intensity in the ligand has reasonably been assigned to ν_{NH} band. Bands at 3 230–3 215 cm⁻¹ are absent in the spectra of Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} on coordination indicating the absence of imino hydrogen and formation of metal nitrogen band in the tautomeric thiol form of the ligand. However, this band of ligand splits after coordination with ZrO²⁺ ion and has been observed at higher frequency. Most probably NH group in these complexes are in different environments and their blue-shifting suggests the absence of bonding through imino nitrogen. Thus, NH group of the ligand is intact in solid complexes.

Blue-shifting of this band also occurs in rest of the complexes.

The strong broad bands at 1 710 cm⁻¹ of ligand is either identical or slightly blue-shifted (by 5–15 cm⁻¹) in all the complexes, suggesting the absence of metal carbonyl oxygen bonding¹¹.

The band at 1 530 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of 2-mercapto-3-substituted-quinazoline-4-one is assigned to thioamide band I of the H–N–C=S group¹² having mixed contribution from δ_{NH} , $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$. This band remains almost unchanged after complexation. However, this band is split or red-shifted (by 5 cm⁻¹) in few cases probably either due to very weak interaction with metal ions or hydrogen bonding of NH group of ligand in the complexes. Band II ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}} + \delta_{\text{CH}}$) experiences a red-shift by 10–20 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes due to increase of CN bond order and decrease of CS bond order¹³ resulting bonding through sulphur. It is further supported by the systematic shifts in thioamide bands III and IV of the ligand. Since these two bands have major contributions from $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$, so they are much affected on coordination. Band III is considerably lowered in intensity or experiences red-shift (by 30–40 cm⁻¹) and band IV is also red-

shifted (30–60 cm^{-1}) with reduced intensity. However, the thioamide bands I and IV are red-shifted by 10–20 and 100–120 cm^{-1} respectively, in all the Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} complexes, suggesting the bonding through imino nitrogen as well as deprotonated thiol sulphur¹⁴. Thus, metal-sulphur bond is assumed in all complexes.

All the MoO_4^{II} and WO_4^{II} complexes show two bands (900, 860) and (880, 850) cm^{-1} assignable to the two $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ and $\text{W}=\text{O}$ stretching modes respectively. The presence of the two bands is consistent with the *cis*-dioxo structure of the MoO_4^{II} and WO_4^{II} groups¹⁵. However, in dioxovanadium(V) complexes, the presence of one medium band at 820–810 cm^{-1} indicates the *trans*-dioxo configuration of the VO_2^{II} group¹⁶. The metal-oxygen multiple bond stretching frequencies of VO_2^{II} species are observed at 970 cm^{-1} but convincing evidence for mononuclear ZrO^{II} group is lacking.

The non-ligand bands at 1 340 and 860 in $[\text{Zr}(\text{TQH})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$, at 1 000, 960, 640 and 490 in $[\text{Zr}(\text{TQH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{SO}_4)_2]$ and at 1 070, 1 000 and 640 in $[\text{VO}(\text{TQH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{SO}_4)]$, suggest the presence of ionic nitrate and unidentate sulphato group¹⁷. Moreover, two characteristic bands around 1 100 cm^{-1} due to ν_3 are expected for unidentate sulphato group. But the ligand displays bands near 1 100 and 1 130 cm^{-1} . So it is very difficult to assign ν_3 for unidentate sulphato group.

The far-infrared spectra of the complexes contain several bands which are present in the spectrum of the ligand also. Hence, it is very difficult to

assign metal-ligand stretching modes in the 600–200 cm^{-1} region. However, new bands at 510, 425 ($\text{Ta}-\text{Cl}$) and 390, 320, 305 cm^{-1} ($\text{Ta}-\text{S}$) in the spectrum of Ta^{V} complex suggest C_{4v} point-group in octahedral structure.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either of AnalaR or chemically pure quality. 2-Mercapto-3-substituted-quinazoline-4-one was prepared by the reported method¹.

All the complexes except those of Nb^{V} and Ta^{V} were prepared using a general method. An alcoholic solution of the metal salt and ligand were mixed using the required molar ratio. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath and its volume reduced to ~50 ml. pH of the mixture was adjusted to 7 (in case of VO^{II} and VO_2^{II} to 6) and digested on a water-bath for 0.5 h. The resulting precipitates were washed with ice-cold ethanol and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator.

The procedure to prepare Nb^{V} and Ta^{V} complexes were somewhat different. NbCl_5 solution was prepared in a mixture of CCl_4 and DMF (10 : 1) and TaCl_5 in methanol. The mixture of metal salt and the ligand solution (in methanol) was stirred at 65° till the evolution of HCl gas. The yellow coloured solution was then cooled at room temperature and 2 N NaOH (4–5 drops) was added to it and stirred for 30 min. The resulting coloured solid complexes were washed with ice-cold methanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 (Table 2).

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis %/(Found/(Calcd.))			
			N	C	H	M
$[\text{VO}(\text{TQH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{SO}_4]$	Black	285	5.00 (5.04)	17.19 (17.29)	1.92 (1.80)	9.30 (9.81)
$[\text{VO}_2(\text{TQH})_2\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$	Marine gray	284	5.53 (5.69)	19.26 (19.51)	1.50 (1.62)	10.56 (10.36)
$[\text{VO}_2(\text{TQH})\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light green	280	7.94 (8.69)	28.73 (28.91)	3.00 (3.01)	15.50 (15.36)
$[\text{VO}_2(\text{TQH})_2]\text{Cl}$	Gray	295	13.54 (13.48)	46.61 (46.20)	2.81 (2.88)	6.42 (6.25)
$[\text{VO}_2(\text{TQPH})_2]\text{Cl}$	Gray	275	9.46 (9.51)	56.99 (57.07)	3.40 (3.39)	5.67 (5.77)
$[\text{VO}_2(\text{TQPH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	Island green	225	8.55 (8.66)	51.90 (52.01)	2.99 (3.40)	7.49 (7.89)
$[\text{Zr}(\text{TQH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{SO}_4)_2]$	Light yellow	>300	10.10 (9.98)	34.21 (34.24)	2.38 (2.37)	11.06 (10.82)
$[\text{ZrO}(\text{TQH})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	Cream	>300	7.59 (7.10)	24.36 (24.37)	2.50 (2.53)	23.01 (23.09)
$[\text{Zr}(\text{TQH})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$	Golden yellow	>300	15.30 (15.34)	35.32 (35.06)	2.51 (2.55)	8.96 (8.39)
$[\text{ZrO}(\text{TQPH})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	White	>300	6.01 (5.96)	35.87 (35.74)	2.97 (2.98)	19.87 (19.36)
$[\text{MoO}_4(\text{TQ})_2]$	Violet	>300	11.89 (11.52)	39.87 (39.50)	1.62 (1.65)	20.11 (19.75)
$[\text{WO}_4(\text{TQ})_2]$	Yellow	>300	10.11 (9.76)	33.32 (33.45)	1.38 (1.39)	32.01 (32.05)
$[\text{WO}_2(\text{TQP})_2]$	Dull white	>300	7.98 (7.71)	46.32 (46.28)	2.43 (2.48)	25.60 (25.34)
$[\text{Nb}(\text{TQH})_2\text{Cl}_4] \cdot \text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light brown	285	8.39 (8.45)	28.99 (29.00)	2.12 (2.42)	14.06 (14.04)
$[\text{Ta}(\text{TQH})_2\text{Cl}_4]\text{Cl}$	White	280	9.25 (9.12)	31.18 (31.27)	1.89 (1.95)	29.85 (29.47)

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurement was made on a Gouy balance. Diamagnetic correction for the ligand molecules were made. Conductance of the complexes ($10^{-3} M$) in DMF were measured using a Wiss Werkstaten Weiheim Obb type LBR conductivity meter.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the grant of Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (R.N.S.).

References

1. G. R. DAVE, G. S. MEWADA and C. AMINE, *J. Indian Chem Soc*, 1960, **37**, 595.
2. A. BUZAS and C. HOFFMAN, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1959, 1889; M. L. GUJRAL and P. N. SEXENA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, **50**, 6662; M. L. GUJRAL, P. N. SEXENA and R. S. TIWARI, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1955, **43**, 637; J. P. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 423; A. F. MCKEY, D. L. GARMAL, R. GAUDRY, H. A. BAKER, G. Y. PARIS, R. W. KEY, G. E. JUST and R. SCHWARTZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4328.
3. B. SINGH, R. J. SINHA and M. M. P. RUKHAIR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 29; B. SINGH, R. N. PANDY, D. K. SHARMA, U. S. P. SHARMA and U. BHANU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 1097.
4. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
5. A. SYAMAL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, **16**, 309; A. P. GIBSBERR, R. C. SHERWOOD and E. KOUBRON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967 **29**, 353.
6. J. SELBIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **65**, 153.
7. C. J. BALLHAUSEN and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.
8. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, New York, 1984, p. 390.
9. U. AGARWALA, B. SINGH and R. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 73.
10. T. M. DUNN, R. S. NYHOLM and S. YAMADA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1564.
11. P. D. SINGH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 23.
12. C. N. R. RAO, R. VENKATARAGHAVAN and T. R. KASTURI, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 36.
13. B. SINGH, R. SINGH, R. V. CHOUDHARY and K. P. THAKUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 174; B. SINGH, H. N. TIWARI, H. H. KHAN and R. N. PANDEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1972, **21**, 315.
14. N. F. CURTIS and Y. M. CRUTIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 804.
15. F. W. MOORE and R. E. PRICE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 2510; B. SOFTRAJANOV, A. NICHOLOVSKS and I. PETRO, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1968, **24**, 1617.
16. G. PAUSEWANG and K. DEHNICKE, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1969, **369**, 265.
17. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1986, pp. 249, 257.